

Low Velocity Impact of Composite Materials Glass Fiber Laminates

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ABSTRACT:

Glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) laminates are crucial in various sectors like aerospace, navigation, automotive, wind power infrastructures because their high strength-to-weight ratio and corrosion resistance. Their susceptibility to impact damage could cause severe structural failures such as delamination, fiber rupture, and matrix fractures which are big risk for public safety. This research focuses structural behavior and failure mechanisms of GFRP laminates under low-velocity impacts to improve industry safety, reliability and performance. Impact experiments were carried out using a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) on panels configured in various fiber orientations, specifically [(0/90)s, (+45/-45)s, and (0/90/+45/-45)s]. Force-time history and impactor velocity, were captured and analyzed to assess the material's resilience and mechanical properties are main key experiments aspects. The purpose of the study to experimental and numerical approach to explore how GFRP laminates react to low-velocity impacts using a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB). Panels in various fiber orientations were tested with impact energies ranging from 1 J to 10 J by using advanced modeling techniques such as progressive damage mechanics, cohesive zone models, and virtual crack closure were implemented in the ABAQUS/Explicit framework to assess internal damages.

Keywords: Glass fiber laminate, low velocity impact, progressive damage mechanics, impact damage, numerical simulation.

Suggested Citation: M. Ahmad, D. Feng, W. Ali, "Low Velocity Impact of Composite Materials Glass Fiber Laminates," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(3), pp. 59-68, May-Jun 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(3\).06](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(3).06)

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials glass fiber laminates are widely studied in the field of materials science. With the development of technology, AI can be used to analyze and predict the low velocity impact behavior of these laminates [1]. Big data can provide a large amount of relevant data for research, helping to better understand the impact characteristics [2]. Digital twin technology can simulate the impact process in a virtual environment, providing more accurate predictions [3]. Additionally, robotics can be employed in testing and experimentation, facilitating the study of low velocity impact on composite materials glass fiber laminates [4]. The qualities of glass fibers and polymers are combined to generate lightweight, highly-strength solutions in fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs), especially glass fiber composites, which have become revolutionary materials in engineering. [5-6].

Originating in the mid-20th century, their development marked a significant advancement, offering an optimal mix of durability and low weight [7]. These composites quickly found applications in industries where such traits are prized, including aerospace, automotive, marine, and civil engineering [8-10]. Despite their advantages, the behavior of glass fiber composites under various

stress conditions, especially low-velocity impacts, presents a complex challenge [11-12]. Such impacts, though not as catastrophic as high-velocity ones, can still cause significant, albeit less visible, damage over time[13]. It is essential to comprehend how these composites behave when subjected to low-speed impacts in order to maintain their durability and structural soundness [14-15].

The split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB), also known as the Kolsky bar, is an important experimental device in the field of materials science and is used to study the complexity of the dynamic response of materials under high strain conditions. Designed for research. The conceptual basis of this method was first proposed by Bertram Hopkinson at the beginning of the 20th century, in 1914 [16-17]. Hopkinson's innovative method was designed to measure the propagation of stress waves through metal rods and laid the foundation for the study of materials under dynamic loading [18]. Herbert Kolsky made further advances and improvements to the technology in 1949. Kolsky's work integrated dual rods (incidence and transmission rods) into the experimental setup, which greatly enhanced the method's ability to accurately measure stress and strain.[19]. This was further bolstered by leveraging then-novel oscilloscope technology for the detailed recording of wave propagation, providing a more nuanced understanding of material behavior under stress.

Composite materials are increasingly used in practical engineering [20]. In the 20th century, the United States began to use composites of fiberglass and resin to manufacture components on aircraft [21-22]. After more than thirty with years of development, my country has achieved considerable progress in fiber composite manufacturing and R&D technology. But compared with foreign countries there is still a big gap in materials research and innovation capabilities. As shown in Figure 1, with the development of aerospace, navigation, wind power generation, as industries such as automobiles, artificial intelligence, and infrastructure continue to develop, the requirements for composite structures and applications are also increasing [23].

Figure 1. The Application of Composite Materials in Various Fields

Laminated composite materials are crafted from layers of fiber-reinforced polymers, each called a ply, which are bonded together to form robust structures[24-25]. Commonly used in aerospace, automotive, and sports, these composites are designed to offer high strength-to-weight ratios. The fibers within these plies, made from materials such as carbon, glass, or aramid, are set in various orientations within an epoxy matrix to optimize mechanical properties[26]. The layups [0/0/90/90] and [0/45/90/-45] are particularly noteworthy. The [0/0/90/90] layup arranges fibers at 0 and 90 degrees alternately, enhancing the laminate's strength and stiffness along those axes, which is ideal for directional load applications. In contrast, the [0/45/90/-45] layout, or quasi-isotropic layup, distributes fibers at 0, 45, 90, and -45 degrees, offering a balanced strength profile in multiple directions, akin to isotropic metals, and suited for complex loading scenarios.

EXPERIMENT SETUP AND HOPKINSON PRESSURE BAR

Materials and Specimen Preparation

Composite materials are commonly employed in aerospace, aviation, etc. due to their good mechanical properties and excellent adaptability. In fields such as shipbuilding and navigation, wind power generation, automobiles, medical care, and infrastructure constructions show in Figure 2. After more than thirty with years of development, my country has achieved considerable progress in fiber composite manufacturing and R&D technology. But compared with foreign countries there is still a big gap in materials research and innovation capabilities. Composite materials properties mention in Table.1.

Table 1. Properties of Different Composites

Ref.	Composite Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m·K)
[27-29]	Reinforced Polymer with Glass Fiber (GFRP)	1.5 - 2.5	500 - 750	100 - 300	20 - 50	0.3 - 1.5
[30-31]	Reinforced Polymer with Carbon Fiber (CFRP)	1.5 - 1.6	1000 - 2500	250 - 600	70 - 250	3.0-15
[32-34]	Polymer Reinforced with Aramid Fiber (AFRP)	1.4 - 1.5	3000 - 4300	100 - 300	70 - 150	0.04 - 0.6
[35-36]	Reinforced Polymer with Basalt Fiber (BFRP)	1.9 - 2.1	484 - 850	300 - 700	40 - 90	1 - 1.5
[37-38]	Polymer Reinforced with Natural Fibers	1.2 - 1.5	50 - 900	25 - 200	3.0-40	0.1 - 0.5

Figure 2. Preparation of Specimen

The layups [0/0/90/90] and [0/45/90/-45] are particularly noteworthy. The [0/0/90/90] layup arranges fibers at 0 and 90 degrees alternately, enhancing the laminate's strength and stiffness along those axes, which is ideal for directional load applications. In contrast, the [0/45/90/-45] layout, or quasi-isotropic layup, distributes fibers at 0, 45, 90, and -45 degrees, offering a balanced strength profile in multiple directions, akin to isotropic metals, and suited for complex loading scenarios. The fabrication of glass fiber laminates begins with the precise cutting and arrangement of glass fiber prepreg tapes, which are tailored to meet exact specifications. These prepreg tapes, infused with a resin matrix, are meticulously layered one over another to form the initial laminate structure in a process designed to optimize the mechanical properties of the final product.

Hopkinson Pressure Bar Testing

In the field of materials science, instrumented Hopkinson Pressure Bar (HPB) machines play an important role, especially when studying the dynamic response of composite materials. This advanced equipment is used to perform low-velocity impact testing of fiberglass laminates, specifically targeting impact energies in the range of approximately 1 to 10 Joules. The setup for these experiments involved placing 80 x 150 mm² panels in a simply supported structure to accurately assess their elasticity under impact conditions, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composite material Damage Failure

Low-velocity impacts on composites often cause delamination, matrix cracking, and fiber breakage, undermining their strength and stiffness. Fiber-matrix debonding can further impair mechanical performance by disrupting internal load transfer. Surface indentations and through-thickness shearing in thicker composites also reduce structural integrity. The severity of these damages depends on the composite's properties, impact conditions, and environmental factors. These issues are critical in maintaining the safety and durability of composite structures.

Low Velocity Impact Results

Figures 4 (a), 5 (a), 6 (a), and 7 (a) show the contact force versus time curves for laminated glass (GF) plates. It is obvious that these curves are asymmetric in all four cases. Furthermore, these figures also show that the peak contact force increases with increasing impact speed and glass layer thickness. As the impact speed increases, the contact force on the laminated glass panel increases.

The corresponding center displacement time history of the GF plate is shown in Figure 1-1(b), Figure 1-2(b), Figure 1-3(b) and Figure 1-4(b). These displacement-time curves also exhibit asymmetric features. It is worth noting that the center displacement of the GF panel increases significantly with the increase of impact speed and mass, and decreases with the decrease of the thickness of the glass layer and PVB interlayer.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Impact Results for Scenario 1

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Impact Results for Scenario 2

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Impact for Scenario 3

Figure 7. Impact for Scenario 4

Table 2 presents a summary of the peak contact force and displacement outcomes for the GF, obtained under different parameter conditions.

Table 2. Summary of Parametric Studies Using Wave Propagation Method (GF plate)

Studied Parameter		Maximum contact force (KN)	Maximum Displacement (mm)
Impact velocity (m/s) Scenario 4	5	15.63	0.86
	20	64.92	3.34
	40	131.83	6.46
Each lass ply thickness (mm) Scenario 5	6	64.92	3.34
	8	103.28	2.13
	10	142.93	1.71
Impactor mass (kg) Scenario 6	0.5	60.21	1.72
	1	64.92	3.34
	2	67.45	6.36
PVC interlayer thickness (mm) Scenario 7	0.38	68.81	3.41
	0.76	64.92	3.34
	1.52	69.24	3.29

Adopted Analytical Model

In realm of Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) experiments, “adopted analytical models” refer to the various theoretical and mathematical frameworks that are utilized to analyze the data gathered from these tests. SHPB technique is primarily used to determine properties of materials under high strain rates, typically seen in impacts or collisions. Below, we discuss several analytical models commonly used in SHPB studies:

One-Dimensional Wave Propagation Model

This foundational model presumes that the stress waves traveling through both bars and test specimen maintain a one-dimensional form. This assumption facilitates the application of wave equations to deduce the specimen’s strain, stress, and strain rate based on the bar’s measured strain.

Key Equations:

$$\text{Strain: } \epsilon = \frac{\Delta L}{L} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Stress: } \sigma = E \cdot \epsilon \tag{2}$$

$$\text{Strain Rate: } \dot{\epsilon} = \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Here, E represents the bar material's modulus of elasticity, ΔL is the change in length, and L is the original length.

Two-Wave Method

This improved model incorporates incident and reflected waves in the input of the specimen bar, along with the transmitted wave in its output. This combination presents a more complete representation of the stress distribution inside the specimen material.

Key Equations:

$$\text{Strain in Specimen: } \epsilon_s = \frac{C_b}{E_s} (\epsilon_i + \epsilon_r + \epsilon_t) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Stress in Specimen: } \sigma_s = E_s \cdot \epsilon_s \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Strain Rate in Specimen: } \dot{\epsilon} = \frac{2C_b}{L_s} (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r) \quad (6)$$

In these equations, C_b is the bar's wave speed, ϵ_i , ϵ_r and ϵ_t represent the strains from incident, reflected, and transmitted waves, respectively. L_s and E_s denote the specimen's length and modulus of elasticity.

Three-Dimensional Correction Models

This category of models accounts for additional complexities such as radial inertia and friction, which are overlooked in simpler models. These factors are particularly relevant for softer materials or when examining very high strain rates.

Considerations

Radial Inertia: Considers the radial expansion of the specimen, which can influence the measured stress.

Friction: Accounts for the interaction between the specimen and the bars, which can introduce shear forces and affect the accuracy of stress measurements.

CONCLUSIONS

Composite laminate structures subjected to low-velocity impacts were analyzed using a split Hopkinson pressure bar. We studied the contact force and center deflection under different parameters. The following conclusions can be drawn from the dynamic response of laminated composite panels under low-velocity impact found in this paper. The force of impact is directly related to the speed and size of the object striking the surface. For small impacts (less than 10 Joules), the initial damage to the composite material and its interface with the aluminum surface is typically limited to small cracks and separation of the layers. As the impact energy increases, damage becomes more severe, with fibers breaking becoming the main way the material is damaged. The first cracks on the back of the material align with the direction of the fibers in the outermost layer of the composite.

Damage failure criteria Damage failure criteria in this research are crucial for predicting the onset and propagation of damage in glass plates under low-velocity impacts, as explored through experimental and numerical methods including wave propagation and finite element analysis.

The arrangement of layers (ply configuration) in aluminum and carbon fiber reinforced composite (CFRP) laminates significantly affects their resistance to impact. Specifically, laminates with alternating (0/45/90/-45) and cross (0/0/90/90) ply configurations have demonstrated enhanced impact resistance. Among the various ply sequences tested, laminates with (0/90) and (± 45) orientations in the CFRP exhibited the best impact resistance, followed by laminates with a (0) orientation.

This study will provide valuable insights that can guide our ongoing research on how different variables influence the initiation and progression of damage in laminated composite materials subjected to low-velocity impacts.

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